

Semantic PEA Data sheet (SPEAD)

Enhancing modular plant documentation with the Asset Administration Shell (AAS)

Sascha Lamm¹, Philipp Wetterich¹, Ingo Dietrich², Sissy Sommer², Peter Pelz¹

¹ Chair of Fluid Systems, Technische Universität Darmstadt

² Industrial Science GmbH

1 Motivation

Modular production represents a transformative approach in the process industry, aimed at meeting the demands of an increasingly dynamic market. This strategy involves breaking down production systems into standardised, pre-fabricated modules, so-called Process Equipment Assemblies (PEAs), that can be rapidly deployed, re-configured, and reused. By adopting modular production, companies significantly reduce time to market, enabling faster responses to changing consumer needs and technological advancements. [1], [2]

1.1 Current state

The structure and the elements of modular process plants are defined through the standard VDI 2776-1 [3]. In Figure 1, the hierarchy of modular plants is depicted on the left side. Components (COMP) are aggregated into Functional Equipment Assemblies (FEAs), which fulfil a single process function, such as conveying, stirring, or heating. FEAs and components are assembled into the aforementioned PEAs by PEA manufacturers or integrators. PEAs realise a process step, such as reacting, transporting, or heating. PEAs must be inherently safe and self-sufficient to ensure exchangeability. The module automation is achieved by use of the Module Type Package (MTP), which is defined in the standard VDI/VDE/NAMUR 2658 [4]. The MTP also acts as the interface between the PEA and the Process Orchestration Layer (POL), which handles the automation of the Modular Plant (MP). [3]

Figure 1: Hierarchy and supply chain of modular production. Suppliers develop components and FEAs, which are integrated by PEA manufacturers. PEA pools allow the operator of the modular plant to scale their laboratory processes into production. Based on VDI 2776-1 [3].

The right side of Figure 1 shows the supply chain in modular plants. PEAs are collected in a PEA pool which contains PEAs for laboratory or production applications. This allows the operator to develop a process in the lab, and subsequently scale it up to production. The production environment can also be reconfigured to meet changing requirements and processes.

The introduction of modularisation into the process industry represents a change in working methods. Responsibilities, for example automation or documentation, are shifted downstream to module and component suppliers. In order to ensure that all involved parties understand the tasks, requirements, and solutions, a high level of digitalisation is necessary. Modules have to be able to communicate with each other and transfer information both within the modular plant itself as well as to outside stakeholders.

This is addressed in the context of Industry 4.0, where digital representations of products and their entire life cycle, also known as digital twins, are of ever-increasing importance. While the process industry has been hesitant in the adaptation of digital twins and the Internet of Things (IoT) [5], [6], research on these topics as well as the utilisation of artificial intelligence (AI) in process planning and engineering has increased steadily. This is evident by the number of ongoing and finished projects in this area, such as ENPRO ORCA¹, KEEN², and ENPRO REUNION³, funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK). The slow adoption of IoT now becomes an advantage: In the process industry, IoT and digital twin technologies are fostered by the owner/operator and the regulatory authorities, yielding a high acceptance within the industry. In contrast, in the manufacturing industry IoT and digital twin technologies are fostered by the supplier, with only little acceptance by the customer. Consequentially, adoption of these technologies in the process industry's supply chain can be expected to increase in the future.

1.2 Making modular production an industrial reality

While modular plants are defined in standards and concepts for modules have been developed, some critical points remain unsolved. Specifically, (i) the availability of hardware modules in the market, (ii) the documentation of modules, and (iii) the approvability of modular plants need to be solved. The ENPRO project REUNION aims to address these points as follows:

Availability of hardware modules

In order to enable modular production and utilise its many benefits, a sufficiently large pool of hardware modules is required (see Figure 1, right). So far, only a limited number of PEAs are available on the market, hindering the wide-spread adaptation of the modular concept. The ENPRO project REUNION aims to develop energy efficient

¹ http://enpro-initiative.de/ENPRO+2_0/ORCA.html

² <https://keen-plattform.de/keen/en/>

³ <http://enpro-initiative.de/ENPRO+Rollout/REUNION.html>

PEAs which fulfil a range of different process steps. In addition to the hardware development in the project, one of the aims is to enable manufacturers to become module builders of the future. For the manufacturers, this also opens up the possibility of providing modules as a service, rather than selling the PEAs to the operators.

Documentation of modules

PEAs have different properties, functions, and requirements. Two PEAs which perform the same process function might vary in their dimensions or operating range. Consequently, the effective and efficient configuration of a modular plant can only be achieved if the capabilities of its components, the modules, are clearly understood. Beyond the engineering, it is also important to know the correct operation, cleaning, and maintenance procedures of the current configuration. For this reason, the available documentation for the plant must be kept up-to-date with the current module configuration. Updates to modules, for example in their automation layer, must also be reflected in the documentation. The required content of module documentation has already been defined in the standard VDI 2776-2, which will be discussed in section 2.1.

Documentation is not only defined by its content, but also by the formal quality of the data it represents. Information must be made available in both human- and machine-readable formats to ensure that the documentation is accessible to all relevant parties. Furthermore, high quality data is a key factor in enabling the digitalisation transformation. In the ENPRO project REUNION, enabling PEA manufacturers and operators to create and utilise high quality documentation is a main focus.

Approvability

One of the main benefits of modular plants is the ability to exchange modules between plants or reuse them for different production processes. As it stands however, each time a modular plant is reconfigured, the entire plant must be approved again. A promising future approach involves granting approval to modules as independent entities and certifying the procedures for module selection and safety evaluation. In REUNION, the approval of modular plants is a main focus. In this paper however, we will not further discuss ongoing developments on this topic.

Focus of this paper

This whitepaper focuses on the documentation of modules. Initially, it outlines the requirements towards PEA documentation as stipulated by the standard VDI 2776-2. Subsequently, we will introduce our proposed solution, and provide some exemplary use-cases to showcase its strengths.

2 Requirements of PEA documentation

In order to avoid building an isolated solution, industry standards and guidelines must serve as the foundation of the documentation. Furthermore, standardised solutions from other areas should be considered to increase reusability and acceptance. In the following sections, we will provide an overview of the documentation requirements for PEAs, outlining how these standards inform our approach.

2.1 Normative requirements

Guidelines for designing modular plants concerning the basic aspects, technical requirements and documentation are outlined in the VDI 2776-2 standard [7]. The documentation of a PEA unlocks the advantages of a modular plant by enabling the selection process for PEAs as well as the approval process of the modular plant. Consequentially, the PEA documentation must at least contain information on the process functions it implements, available services, interface requirements, as well as the area of intended use. PEA documentation should be as detailed as necessary to avoid problems for the operator. PEA documentation must reflect the life cycle of the PEA in all aspects and enable the operator to orchestrate, evaluate, operate and maintain modular plants. As mentioned in section 1.2, the concept of modularity in process plants also introduces new business cases for stakeholders, such as leasing PEAs from a pool of PEAs. The documentation is a crucial component in enabling operators and PEA manufacturers to utilise this potential.

The documentation of the plant automation must be structured in such a way that it is clear which services are available, how these services are organised, and how they depend on each other. Services must be described according to VDI/VDE/NA-MUR 2658 part 4 [4], and the documentation must reflect which process functions a service consists of. A P&I diagram including the representation of the processing functions and electrical circuits must be included, ideally in an open data format such as DEXPI P&ID.

It is essential that all information related to a PEA is provided as a single unit, rather than being fragmented across the individual components. The aggregated information, derived from the documentation of the components and FEAs that constitute the PEA, is to be combined into a single comprehensive PEA data sheet.

Finally, the VDI 2776-2 standard formulates no requirements towards the format and metadata that the documentation must be adhere to. Instead, it refers to the VDI 2770 standard, which defines minimum requirements for the exchange and means of exchange of digital manufacturer information. According to VDI 2770, documents must be classified according to their type and purpose. Documentation must be provided in a single documentation container, which contains one or more containers with the individual documents and metadata files. The minimum metadata are a document ID, a domain for the document ID, the aforementioned document classification, as well as a reference to the real-life object. [8]

2.2 Further requirements

As outlined by VDI 2776-2, the PEA documentation should be an aggregation of information into a single data sheet [7]. In addition to the requirements given by the standardisation bodies, we propose further requirements that such a PEA data sheet should fulfil.

First, the PEA data sheet must be a single point of truth. The information contained within documents should not be duplicated in other documents. Especially for new PEAs, this is crucial, since updates for example in the automation to improve functionality or solve issues are likely to occur. Thus, instead of containing the information itself, the PEA data sheet should only include references to the information. This ensures that updates to the documentation of a component or FEA are automatically reflected in the PEA data sheet.

Second, it is evident that not all parties involved in the manufacturing, approval and operation of a modular plant are interested in all aspects of the PEA documentation. Users of the PEA data sheet should be able to constrain their view of the data sheet to the information relevant to their specific use-case. This way, information can be found more quickly and precisely.

Third, as mentioned in the beginning of this chapter, our objective is to avoid building an isolated solution which only works for a limited number of use-cases. Our solution must be highly acceptable for all stakeholders. Thus, we require the documentation to adhere to the so-called FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles. Information contained within documents must be findable to facilitate efficient use. It must be accessible to all authorised parties in widely accepted formats. Data must be usable in different contexts, whether it is accessed by a machine or a human. Lastly, in order to support the digitalisation of modules, information must be reusable across different domains.

Finally, the recently passed Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 will require manufacturers to provide a digital product pass for their products in the near future. This pass must include, amongst others, a unique product identifier, manuals and safety information [9]. Digitalised PEA documentation supports manufacturers and suppliers in creating such a digital product pass.

3 Semantic PEA Data sheet (SPEAD)

With the requirements and application scenarios outlined, we proposed the introduction of a **Semantic PEA Data Sheet (SPEAD)**, originally presented at the Annual Meeting of Process Engineering and Materials Technology 2024 (PEMT 2024) [10]. In the following, we will give a brief introduction into technologies involving semantics, and describe how semantics can be used to create a PEA data sheet that is suitable to the needs of modular production.

3.1 A short introduction to semantic technologies

Semantics is a discipline which studies the meaning of language and symbols. It aims to understand how words, sentences and texts convey meaning in different contexts. In computer science, semantics are used to enable machines to interpret data. The meaning of data is conveyed via semantic web technologies such as Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Web Ontology Language (OWL). At the core of RDF stands the semantic triple of subject-predicate-object, which is shown in Figure 2. [11]

Figure 2: A semantic triple, comprised of subject - predicate - object. The example is shown with corresponding vocabulary from Schema.org (schema prefix) [12].

By linking subject and object through the predicate, a directed graph, also known as a knowledge graph, is created [11]. The nodes and edges in this graph are described through vocabularies [11]. Vocabularies are predefined descriptions of the meaning of resources, and are oftentimes summarised into ontologies [11]. Ontologies are available online and contain uniform resource identifiers (URI), which clearly identify vocabularies, thus making them universally understandable and making them interoperable by providing them in RDF format [11]. Examples of such ontologies include the Dublin Core ontology (DCMT) as a generalised descriptor of arbitrary resources [13], the friend-of-a-friend (FOAF) ontology for linking people and information [14], and the quantity, unit, dimension and type (QUDT) ontologies which describe physical quantities, units of measure and their dimensions [15].

Today, semantics and related technologies are primarily used in semantic web applications. They are used to augment web-based resources by providing additional metadata and context. For example, Google maintains a massive knowledge graph which enhances its Google Search engine [16]. Standardisation efforts for semantic web technologies are led by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).

3.2 Using semantics to create a PEA data sheet

Implementing semantic links to connect information and documents enables that the content of documents can be mirrored in the PEA data sheet without duplication. Furthermore, by using pre-defined and widely accepted ontologies, the PEA data sheet can be understood by both machine and human and across different companies and contexts. The localisation of resources or information can easily be achieved through uniform resource locators (URLs) or uniform resource identifiers (URIs).

Figure 3: Information contained within documents is linked semantically to a knowledge graph via URIs/URLs. This graph uses well defined and widely accepted ontologies and vocabularies to describe information nodes and their connections to increase interoperability as well as human- and machine-readability.

By linking information and documents semantically, a knowledge graph that describes all aspects of a PEA can be generated, see Figure 3. This graph can be used to generate different views depending on user specifications. Additionally, it is possible to make logical deductions from the semantic links between semantically described information. This process is called semantic reasoning or semantic inference. Finally, the graph can be integrated into an AI pipeline that uses a technique called Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), which enables a Large Language Model (LLM) to retrieve information from the graph, enhancing its capabilities. These technologies can enhance the PEA selection and matching process. For example, a plant engineer could ask a RAG supported LLM to find all PEAs from a given PEA pool that match a given process.

3.3 Integration of the SPEAD in the Asset Administration Shell

Linking information and documents semantically is a considerable additional effort that has to be performed by the manufacturer of a PEA or plant engineers. To improve the acceptance of our solution, SPEAD must rely on technology that is already accepted. For this reason, SPEAD will be integrated into the so-called Asset Administration Shell (AAS).

What is the Asset Administration Shell?

The AAS is a digital twin of an industrial asset which contains all information related to this asset across its entire life cycle [16]. It offers controlled access to this information, and unambiguously identifies the asset. The information is mapped to different

submodels, each with a different purpose. The submodels are semantic representations of already established information models such as VDI-guidelines or defacto industry standards.

The interaction with the AAS can be categorised into three different types as shown in Figure 4: First, the AAS can be used passively as an exchange format. Secondly, AAS' can be stored remotely, for example in the manufacturer's digital infrastructure, and be made available through an API. This type of AAS is called reactive AAS. Finally, a third type of AAS, also known as proactive AAS, is currently in development. Different AAS' will be able to communicate with each other and request information through Industry 4.0 communication protocols. [16]

Figure 4: Types of Asset Administration Shells. Passive AAS' (Type 1) can be used as an exchange file format. Reactive AAS' (Type 2) can be accessed through APIs. Proactive AAS' (Type 3) are able to communicate with each other through Industry 4.0 communication protocols. Type 1 and 2 are currently available, while type 3 is still in development.

The AAS is developed and maintained by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA), a group consisting of over 120 members from different industries. Submodels are proposed by community members and evaluated by the IDTA. As of March 2025, there are 93 registered submodels actively in development, published, or proposed. [16]

Since the registered submodels cover topics from a large variety of areas, not all submodels are relevant for modular plants. We identified four key submodels that contain information which must be represented in a SPEAD. The submodel "Handover Documentation" contains all documents pertaining to an asset, such as installation, operation, or maintenance manuals, but also certificates like CE conformity or ATEX certificates [17]. Furthermore, the submodel standardises the metadata that comes with the documentation, as it is based on the previously introduced standard VDI 2770 [17]. Other relevant submodels are the submodel "Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment" [18], the submodel "Inclusion of Module Type Package" [19], as well as the "Carbon Footprint" submodel [20], which contain information on asset nameplate, the module automation, and environmental impact of a module respectively.

Future-proofing PEA documentation

While the AAS is still a new technology, we believe it to be a key technology for future-proofing PEA documentation. Systems and applications such as engineering software,

plant design software, and Enterprise-Resource-Planning (ERP) systems are not yet compatible with the AAS. However, due to the strong development effort already present in the AAS community, it is logical to expect such systems to add compatibility with the AAS in the future, which in turn ensures the interoperability of SPEAD with such systems.

Furthermore, the AAS is especially interesting due to the recent introduction of Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 on ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, which establishes the digital product pass [9]. In collaboration with ZVEI e. V., the IDTA has proposed the “Digital Product Pass for Industry 4.0” (DPP4.0). The DPP4.0 utilises the AAS as a structured representation of product information for a specific product, which can be accessed via the ID link situated on the product.⁴

SPEAD in the AAS

To implement SPEAD, we first developed a metamodel which structures the SPEAD into different categories. Specifically, we identified the following areas:

1. **Operating ranges:** The conditions under which the PEA can be operated. This does not only include process-specific information like minimum and maximum temperatures or pressure ranges, but also environmental conditions like humidity and medium-specific requirements such as pH limits.
2. **Interfaces:** The connections of a PEA to other PEAs or the infrastructure. Relevant interfaces include material interfaces, power connections, and ports for information exchange.
3. **Functions:** The available functions and services a PEA can provide. For example, a conveying module might have multiple services available to enable batch and continuous transportation of a medium.
4. **Safety and security:** Certificates and information regarding conformity to regulatory statutes. Examples include ATEX certificates, IP codes, and compliance with directives like TA Luft.
5. **Construction:** Information on the physical construction of the PEA. Included are physical dimensions as well as material certificates.

The information that these categories include can be drawn from existing sources. For example, data regarding operating ranges might be contained in a technical data sheet, while the PEAs services can be found in the MTP file. Data might also be spread between different documents. Lastly, information from one of the categories can also depend on information from a different category. By unifying these different information sources into a singular collection, SPEAD aligns with the requirement imposed by the standard VDI 2776-2 of a single comprehensive PEA data sheet, which was outlined in section 2.1. Additionally, our requirement of SPEAD being a single point of truth, see section 2.2, is fulfilled.

⁴ Detailed information on the DPP4.0 can be found online: <https://dpp40.eu/>

The Asset Administration Shell offers the ideal starting point for populating the meta-model of SPEAD with actual information. SPEAD will be implemented as a submodel, and data present in other submodels can be referenced by means of semantic links. The submodels “Digital Nameplate for industrial equipment”, “Handover Documentation”, “Inclusion of Module Type Package”, and “Carbon Footprint” are of particular interest, as they contain relevant documents pertaining to a specific PEA. The integration of the SPEAD submodel into the AAS and its connections to other submodels is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The Semantic PEA Data sheet (SPEAD) in the Asset Administration Shell (AAS). SPEAD unifies the information contained in different submodels, such as the “Digital Nameplate for industrial equipment” and the “Handover Documentation” submodels, by connecting them through semantic links. Consequentially, no additional information must be provided to populate the SPEAD submodel.

Notably, the submodel “Generic Frame for Technical Data for Industrial Equipment in Manufacturing” [21] is missing from the list of relevant submodels. While this submodel provides a generalised framework for including technical data in the AAS, it leaves the specification of technical properties to the user. This stands in opposition to our requirement of a FAIR semantic data sheet for PEAs, since it does not constrain the terminologies used to describe technical properties to a well-defined and interoperable vocabulary.

Consider the following scenario: two different manufacturers offer conveyor modules. One of them provides the rate at which a volume of medium is transported as a “flow rate” given in millilitres per minute, the other calls this value “volume flow” and provides it in microlitres per second. While it might be clear to a human user that these two names reference the same technical property, the machine-readability suffers from the inconsistent terminology. Further, simply stating the unit of a value in textual form does not inform a machine directly about its relation or conversion formulas to other units.

SPEAD alleviates this issue by utilising a clearly defined ontology. The terms used in this ontology is derived from existing ontologies where possible. For example, the description of the unit of a technical property is achieved through the QUDT ontologies, which provide the necessary information to convert between both non-SI and SI units

[15]. SPEAD thus relies on existing and accepted technology to achieve FAIR PEA documentation.

In this whitepaper, we outline the requirements and conceptual design of SPEAD. The realisation, which includes the design of the underlying information model as well as the implementation of SPEAD as an AAS-submodel, is part of further work in the ENPRO project REUNION.

3.4 Use-cases for SPEAD

There is a plethora of use-cases for PEA documentation enhanced by a semantic digital twin. We identified three specific use-cases which we view as those with the most potential: PEA matching, approval, as well as metric and KPI generation. Note that these are not the only use-cases, and further application scenarios are feasible.

PEA matching

SPEAD enables process engineers to easily identify PEAs which match the process steps of their processes. For example, a process could have a pressure range that is required for its safe and efficient execution. Since SPEAD represents the operating range of a PEA, checking whether a given PEA's maximum or minimum operating pressure is exceeded by the process is trivial. Furthermore, the requirements of a PEA towards its non-modular environment are included in SPEAD, and can thus be compared to the capabilities of an operator's manufacturing infrastructure.

Approval

The approval of a plant is a lengthy process which involves many stakeholders, such as the operators or the authorities. For this process to go as fast as possible, it is essential that all relevant information and documentation is readily available. In particular, certificates and conformity declarations pertaining to the safety and security of the plant are of importance. SPEAD can aid this process by constraining the view of the documentation to only those documents relevant to a stakeholders use case.

Metrics and KPIs

Since all functions and requirements of a PEA are modelled in SPEAD, it is possible to compare the PEAs implementation of a process step to a reference process. This allows the operator or manufacturer of a PEA to measure, evaluate and display its efficiency through metrics like energy KPIs. Additionally, the inclusion of the "Carbon Footprint" submodel in the AAS enables stakeholders to assess the carbon footprint of the entire plant, and integration of the plant's footprint into the carbon footprint of a product becomes possible.

4 Outlook

Modelling the characteristics and functions of a PEA is an important step towards PEA matching, modular plant approval and PEA evaluation. However, PEAs are not the only essential component of a modular plant. It is evident that both the process a PEA or a group of PEAs are to fulfil as well as the non-modular infrastructure that the PEAs are placed into must be understood in detail. This interaction is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Venn diagram showing the interaction between semantically described processes, modules, and infrastructure.

A possible approach to model the process is a Semantic Process Data sheet, similar to the proposed Semantic PEA Data sheet. Process parameters, requirements, products and educts could be described and linked semantically, thus making the process understandable for humans and machines, as well as enabling the automatic matching of PEAs to the process.

It is feasible that not all processes and PEAs could be safely operated in any given infrastructure. Some processes might require suction exhausts to get rid of toxic fumes, or a PEA might rely on coolant circulation to operate. Consequentially, it is crucial to understand the infrastructure both from an engineering as well as a regulatory perspective. A semantic model of the infrastructure could make such information available and be used to match PEAs and processes accordingly.

The future of modular production in the process industry

Modular production in the process industry and Industry 4.0 are still in their infancy. In the future, component and PEA manufacturers will enhance their products by supplying an AAS alongside it. These AAS can be integrated and extended with additional submodels by module manufacturers to reflect the aggregation to a PEA. PEAs with corresponding AAS can be used by process developers and engineers to match PEAs to processes. The AAS can then be utilised to provide the necessary documentation to the authorities for approval. Finally, operators can integrate PEAs and their AAS

into their own asset management, and retrieve information as needed during the entire life cycle of a PEA. In Figure 7, we outline this vision of the future graphically.

Figure 7: Hierarchy and supply chain of modular production with the Asset Administration Shell. Suppliers deliver components and FEAs with AAS, which is integrated into a PEAs AAS. PEAs are aggregated into a PEA pool, with which process developers can perform PEA matching. Documentation of the selected PEAs can be taken from the respective AAS and supplied to the authorities for approval and to the operators for production. Structure based on VDI 2776-1 [3].

The introduction of modules into the process industry enables further business cases. For example, pools of PEAs could be made available across company boundaries. PEA owners could lease their PEAs to other companies, or offer the purchasing of operating hours for PEAs. All of these possible business cases require sufficient documentation, since they focus primarily on the provision of PEA functions rather than the development of PEAs. The AAS is an ideal solution, since it can easily be provided to a customer without requiring large amounts of paper documents. [7]

5 Summary

Modular production is transforming the process industry by improving flexibility, efficiency, and scalability. By structuring production systems into standardized Process Equipment Assemblies (PEAs), companies can reduce time to market and adapt more easily to changing demands. However, challenges such as module availability, proper documentation, and regulatory approval remain barriers to widespread adoption. The project ENPRO REUNION addresses these issues by developing energy-efficient PEAs, enhancing documentation practices, and supporting the creation of new approval processes.

Our key innovation, the Semantic PEA Data Sheet (SPEAD), integrates with the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) to create a structured, machine-readable digital twin of PEAs. This enables improved PEA selection, performance evaluation, and simplifies the approval process. Looking ahead, modular production, supported by digitalisation and Industry 4.0 technologies, will not only fundamentally change the manufacturing process, but also introduce new business models such as PEA leasing and service-based usage, ensuring a more adaptive and efficient process industry.

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